

A geochemical investigation and control management of saline water intrusion in the coastal aquifer of Purba Midnapur district in West Bengal, India

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Abstract : The coastal groundwater storage of Purba Midnapur district in West Bengal, India is deteriorated as regards to quality and quantity as a severe risk to excessive overdraft due to ingress of saline water into fresh water aquifers. Here it is found that the upper soil horizon is of quaternary origin and consists of alternating deposits of clay and sand of marine origin. As with all marine deposits, rounded grains and high porosity are dominant characteristics. The mixture of alluvial and marine deposits soil characteristics has been found in the northern part of district. Also there is a great spatial heterogeneity in the aquifer. The coastal line up to 5 to 40 km wide tract has been contaminated due to the movement of saline water in the fresh water aquifers, as result groundwater becomes unused for irrigation and drinking for domestic purposes. The groundwater samples from the northern side of Purba Midnapur near the Rupnarayan River have been collected and analyzed at the chemical laboratory of State Water Investigation Directorate, Government of West Bengal. From the chemical analysis, it is clear that the values of concentration of dissolved solids, chloride and iron exist above or more than permissible limits. The contour lines for chloride concentration are drawn based on the chemical analysis. The above properties are compared with the drinking water standards set by World Health Organization. Based on the results, it is concluded that various prevention and control techniques would be implemented into the study area. This paper also suggests methodology for controlling saline water intrusion in the area concern.

Keywords : Geology, soil characteristics, saline water intrusion, chemical analysis, control management.

I. Introduction

The Purba Midnapur district (Fig. 1) in West Bengal is located to the southwest of Calcutta and shares the western border of the state of Orissa. The district comprises 6724 km² area and bordered by Paschim Midnapur and Bankura districts of West Bengal in the north, Hooghly, Howrah and 24-Paragnas districts of West Bengal in the east, Bay of Bengal in the south and Mayurbhanj and Balasore district of Orissa in the southwest. The district lies roughly between 21' 31" to 23' 00" N and 86' 45" to 88' 00" E. It is found that the coastal subsurface **layer** of Purba Midnapur district aquifers continued from the inland part of the district up to the coast. It is also seen that there is considerable lateral varia-

tion, i.e. the individual layer of sand, laterally changes its grade from sandy to silt/clay and it is also observed that the three different type of formations encountered in various and the district belong to different geological ages, from tertiary to the recent, consists of alternating deposits of clay and sand of marine origin. As with all marine deposits, rounded grains and high porosity are dominant characteristics. The northern part of the district consists of a mixture of alluvial and marine deposits.

The coarse sediments form the aquifer materials. The aquifer extends down to a depth of 285 m below land surface. Groundwater occurs under unconfined condition within the sandy horizon, which is sandwiched between the clay horizons.

The groundwater extraction as a sustainable point of view as requirements for various sectors is much critical issue at a days. Seawater intrusion and perched aquifer containing saline soil are main cause of ground water pollution. The purified water supplied by the Public Health Engineering Department and Geomakhali water treatment plant is insufficient for the industries and general population, hand pumps and heavy-duty pumps are tapping groundwater. Eight numbers of water samples and one sea water sample were collected from different deep tube wells for studying the physico-chemical properties of the groundwater in the area (Table 1).

The significant contributions related to the present field of investigation were collected and critically studied. These works are categorized under four groups such as : (i) theoretical contribution, (ii) laboratory-based experimental works, (iii) field based **observations** and (iv) application of management techniques to control saline water intrusion. **The data were taken from various sources and e-resources like technical publications in journals – seminars**

and interviews from senior academicians. Amongst significant contribution in the relevant area of investigation, the work of some previous researchers have been found to be worthy of note¹⁻¹¹. A few researchers worked on effect on groundwater due to saline water intrusion phenomenon in coastal areas for South 24-Parganas district, West Bengal¹²⁻¹⁵.

After reviewing the above literatures¹⁻¹⁵ on the research of saline water intrusion, the most relevant research works have been discussed here. Earlier it was suggested that the skimming well with horizontal collector system was a viable solution for preventing salt water encroachment into inland fresh water aquifer¹⁶. The industrial zone of the city of Herakleio in Greek islands, the encroachment of saline water were prevented and proposed different management scenarios by Papadopoulou and also suggested artificial recharge of fresh water as part of solution¹⁷.

The position and character of salt water and fresh water interface were studied at the groundwater bodies within the aquifer of Digha beach of Purba

Table 1. The physico-chemical properties of collected water samples from eight tube wells and one from sea

Sl. No.	Area/Blocks	pH	Specific conductivity ($\mu\text{mhos/cm}$ at 25°C)	Carbonate CO_3^- (ppm)	Bicarbonate HCO_3^- (ppm)	Chloride (Cl^-) (ppm)	Total Hardness as CaCO_3 (ppm)	Iron Fe^{3+} (ppm)	TDS (ppm)	Cl/ $(\text{HCO}_3 + \text{CO}_3)$
1.	Betkundu P.H. No. 1	7.55	4700	Nil	250	1580	660	0.3	3008	6.32
2.	Dhekua P.H. No. 2	7.71	910	Nil	280	150	100	0.2	582	0.54
3.	Natsal P.H. No. 1	7.67	3900	Nil	200	1220	560	2.0	2496	6.10
4.	Gopalpur P.H. No. 1	7.71	920	Nil	230	100	40	2.0	589	0.43
5.	Laksha P.H. No. 1	7.65	970	Nil	250	140	50	0.2	621	0.56
6.	Chattanyapur P.H. No. 1, Zone-1	8.64	1590	60	140	450	240	Nil	1018	2.25
7.	Chattanyapur P.H. No. 1, Zone-2	7.54	1010	Nil	200	160	440	Nil	646	0.80
8.	Nandakumar P.H. No. 1	7.31	3100	Nil	100	950	560	0.2	1984	9.50
9.	Sea water	7.80	26000	Nil	180	11400	3570	0.72	16640	63.330

Table 2. Drinking water quality standards (WHO)

Sl. No.	Water sample parameter	WHO International Standards, 1971 Permissible limit (maximum)/range
1.	pH	6.5–9.2
2.	Specific conductance in $\mu\text{mhos}/\text{cm}$ at 25°C	–
3.	Carbonate CO_3^{2-} in ppm	10
4.	Bicarbonate HCO_3^- in ppm	100–800
5.	Chloride Cl^- in ppm	600
6.	Total Hardness CaCO_3 in ppm	500
7.	Iron Fe^{3+} in ppm	1.0
8.	Total Dissolved Solids (TDS) in ppm	1500

Midnapur in West Bengal. The interface depth between salt water and fresh water in the Digha beach was estimated to be much less than that determined on the basis of the Ghyben-Herzberg formula¹⁸.

Very recently the groundwater quality assessment and saline water intrusion were studied in the coastal zones of district of Purba Midnapur, West Bengal⁹. Water samples were considerably hard as per chemical analysis results (between 410–1500 ppm) as regard to CaCO_3 concentration. The salinity was delineated by chloride concentration (Cl^-) and total dissolved solids measurements.

II. Materials and methods

A. Observations of the present work

Almost all the theories developed for saline water intrusion have been for homogenous, isotropic aquifers, a condition not found in Purba Midnapur district, which is characterized by special heterogeneity of the aquifer. As a result, filaments of high hydraulic conductivity protrude deep inland from the sea causing encroachment saline water inland in the course of this preferably passageway. This orientation of these filaments inland is often curvilinear with sharp bends and changes in directions occurring sometimes. In view of the great heterogeneity of the aquifer, it is very difficult, if not impossible to apply the saline water ingress theories for a homogenous aquifer to the coastal aquifer of Purba Midnapur. The importance of collection of water samples and their chemical analyses arises in this context as shown in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. Study area showing the locations of sampling points.

Sodium chloride (NaCl) is a relatively stable compound, which does not chemically react with most aquifer minerals. As a result the concentration of sodium chloride is mainly governed by interaction and the equilibrium involving in fresh water and salt water, in other words, knowing the saline concentration of sea water, any other saline concentration can be interspersed as the result of mixing sea water and freshwater in a certain ratio. Ideally, water sample should be taken at average depths 200 m and at different locations in coastal area of Purba Midnapur to obtain the salinity at different points in the aquifer underneath there. However, for doing these drilling of boreholes is required, which is expensive and time-consuming. To expedite the process of characterization of salinity of the aquifer, it is chosen to utilize the deep tube wells installed by the Public Health Engineering Directorate, Government of West Ben-

gal to obtain water samples that are subsequently analysed chemically. From the chemical analysis of the water samples, the chloride concentration of each of the samples can be ascertained.

III. Results and discussion

The general geographical feature of Purba Midnapur district under is very flat terrain with the ground heights at most places very slightly higher than the sea. Two rivers, Haldi to the south and Rupnarayan to the north, allow for saline water ingress. Saline water also enters into the aquifer through the highly porous coastal deposits near Narghat. The aquifer is heterogeneous to the point of being almost randomly distributed. In this context, the ingress of seawater is closely understood from a geochemical analysis. This analysis was carried out through a collection of water from tube wells of depth of approximately 200 m (600 ft) from the coastal areas and subjecting the water to a chemical analysis. The results of the chemical analysis (Table 1) show that the chloride (Cl^-) concentration in that area is highly variable. Given that the only source of Cl^- is the sea (due to the absence of Cl^- bearing rocks in the area); the Cl^- concentration may be attributed to a balance between the freshwater and the intruded seawater locally. **The sodium chloride (NaCl) is normally present in water in the form of chloride ion.** The chloride concentration above 600 mg/L (Table 2) generates a obvious salt taste in drinking water. For sample numbers 1 to 9 (sea water) the chloride values in ppm are 1580, 150, 1220, 100, 140, 450, 160, 950 and 11400 respectively. So for seawater sample, maximum chloride value is 11400 ppm. It is obvious that the increase of chloride content is due to the salt-water intrusion in the coastal side.

As per Table 2, 1500 ppm is the permissible limit of TDS in drinking water. The amount of TDS in sample numbers 1 to 9 are 3008, 582, 2496, 589, 621, 1018, 646, 1984 and 16640, in ppm respectively. Therefore saline water intrusion is responsible for the higher level of TDS concentration in the coastal area. The water samples are classified as saline, brackish and fresh water depending on the presence of TDS in water.

If sulphate, chloride and nitrates of calcium or magnesium are present in water, such hardness is known as permanent hardness. The permissible values of hardness of water as CaCO_3 in ppm are 500 ppm as per Table 2. For sample numbers 1, 3, 7, 8 and 9 the hardness in ppm are 660, 560, 440, 560 and 3570 ppm respectively. It is obvious that seawater intrusion takes place in this area.

A. Coastal groundwater management

Coastal groundwater management aiming towards control of saltwater intrusion are carried out with the objective of limiting the fresh water withdrawal whereby preventing further intrusion of saline water into the freshwater zone. The conventional methods widely used around the world include the following : (i) Creation of hydraulic barriers, (ii) Canal irrigation, (iii) Desalination and reverse osmosis, (iv) Rain-water harvesting and (v) Artificial recharge methods. The hydraulic barriers are created by keeping the basin water level high, initiating a fresh water ridge near the sea, creating a pumping trough or extraction barrier trough, or development of a semi pervious barrier. Canal irrigation is one of the principal methods used for improving the growth of the crop. Adopting this irrigation technique not only can eliminate the use of deep tube wells for irrigation, but also the seepage of fresh water into the ground push back the saline water while controlling the upconing. Owing to the lack of cost competitiveness, desalination is considered only when all the other methods have been ruled out for various reasons. There are several methods of desalination such as distillation, vapour compression, solar distillation, freezing, electro-dialysis and reverse osmosis. Rain-water harvesting and conservation involve preservation and accumulation of rain water directly.

The collected rainwater can be accumulated in the surface or subsurface for future usage with the aim to minimize the loss due to surface runoff through drains and drainage channels to the nearby rivers and/or sea. The process in which groundwater reservoir is replenished at a higher rate than that of natu-

ral conditions is called artificial groundwater recharge. The various methods of artificial recharge include spreading, recharge shafts, injection wells, induced recharge, etc. The selection of a particular method is determined by local topography, hydrogeology and availability of freshwater for recharge. The authors have developed a cost-effective and convenient methodology for coastal groundwater management. While the details of the model have been published elsewhere, the salient features are described here.

Fig. 2. Control management : Option A : Excessive recharge and pushing away or saltwater front; Option B : Excessive withdrawal encroaches the saltwater front.

The methodology is suitable specifically for coastal regions having significant annual precipitation, good hydraulic conductivity of the aquifer, low depth of fresh groundwater and not very urbanized area. The technique (see Fig. 2) involves : (i) withdrawal of freshwater by qanat-well structure since shallow wells are unsuitable for low yield and adoption of deep tube wells initiates the problem of upconing, and (ii) the refilling of groundwater in recharge ponds and recharge wells by rainwater. It may be observed from the figure below, neither of the options A and B is desirable. For optimum usage of this innovative technique, adequate balance should be maintained between the withdrawal of freshwater and the recharge by precipitation and drainage of used water. This demands a factor of safety above unity. Factor of safety was defined as the ratio of water available for recharge to that of withdrawal in a specified period.

IV. Conclusion

Saline water ingress into the fresh water aquifer occurs in Purba Midnapur district under West Bengal state in India. Rapid increase industrial sectors, growing population and agriculture sectors fresh water are needed. For prevention, control and uniform management of fresh water supply the following measures to be implemented.

The nature of variation has been observed to be irregular for the chloride concentration in the case of aquifer lying 200 m below ground level. The concentration of chloride is found quite high in some locations like Betkundu (1580 ppm), Natsal (1220 ppm), Nandakumar (950 ppm) and Chattanyapur (450 ppm). On the contrary, the chloride concentration is very low in some locations like Dhekua (150 ppm), Gopalpur (100 ppm) and Laksha (140 ppm). This heterogeneity in the aquifer media of the study area has attributed to this irregularity of the contours for chloride concentration.

As per WHO, permissible value of hardness of water as CaCO_3 is 500 ppm. For sample numbers 1, 3, 8 and 9 the hardness in ppm are 660, 560, 560 and 3570 ppm respectively. It is obvious that seawater intrusion takes place in this area. The nature of variation has been observed to be irregular for the specific conductivity concentration in the case of aquifer lying 200 m below ground level. The concentration of specific conductivity is quite high in some locations like Betkundu (4700 $\mu\text{mhos/cm}$) and along the Rupnarayan River bank specific conductivity concentration is 4000 $\mu\text{mhos/cm}$.

To mitigate fresh coastal groundwater contamination, it is important to analyse and control saltwater intrusion into aquifers lying below. In this regard various hydrological and geological investigations and groundwater assessments have been made in the study area. The observed wide variation in saline concentration revealed high degree of spatial heterogeneity of the aquifers. Although different technique is available. Here a convenient methodology has been developed for the management of groundwater in the coastal area that involved withdrawal of fresh water by qanat well structure and subsequent rainwater recharge.

In summer season, there is heavy drawdown of water table, resulting in acute scarcity of fresh groundwater in the regions surrounded by Rupnarayan River and Haldi River. It is proposed that the upstream river water of the both rivers may be suitable used after proper treatment for various purposes like domestic use, Irrigation and Industries etc.

Optimization of pumping, proper arrangement of pattern and reshuffling of point of withdrawal.

Injection well or water spreading techniques as means of artificial recharge creates fresh water ridge to prevent saline water intrusion.

Pumping trough in the zone between extraction area and the coast has been developed to minimize the salt water ingress.

At rooftops rainwater is collected and recharge to aquifers and is used after light treatment.

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